

Orientation preserving fibers

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§0 Conventions

By “orientation-preserving,” we mean that for two fibers, $\{f, g\}$, the map $\zeta: f \rightarrow g$ is C_p^∞ -linear. We operate under the convention that $\pi_0(\mathbf{Or}) \simeq \pi_k(\mathbf{Or})$ for all natural values of k , and where $\mathbf{Or}$ is the category of orientation-preserving fibers. For arithmetic multiplication and division, we always write the product

$$\mathcal{K}_\alpha \odot \mathcal{K}_\beta \text{ (mult.)}; \mathcal{K}_\alpha \odot^{-1} \mathcal{K}_\beta \text{ (divis.)}$$

We require that $\alpha \mathbf{R} \beta$ induces a preorder, and a total ordering whence the relationship is equality.

If a map (of set-enriched objects) is *not* orientation-preserving, then there is a limit

$$q_{filt} = \lim_{0 \rightarrow Inf(i)} \Omega_i^j,$$

and an object $\hat{q}$ which corresponds to the immersion

$$q_{filt} \hookrightarrow S\text{Sets}_\Sigma.$$

If $\hat{q} \Rightarrow \hat{q}$ is a 2-cell, then there is an exact section

$$\hat{q}\mathbb{B} \rightarrow \hat{q}.$$

If we wish to grade this map, we must split it.

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \hat{q}\mathbb{B} & \xrightarrow{\quad} & \hat{q} \\ & \mathbf{1} & \\ \emptyset \downarrow & & \\ \hat{q}|_0 & & \end{array}$$

§1 Filters

For every coupling $\hat{q}R\mathbb{B}$, there is an automatic bijection $\hat{q}_{KER} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{B}|_{\{\emptyset,1\}}$ due to the induced Koszul¹ connection

$$\hat{q}_{KER} \xrightarrow{Kosz} \text{int}(\mathbb{B}) \simeq \mathcal{K}_1$$

Definition 1.0.1. A *filter* is a faithful extension of a monad such that $\mathfrak{M}_{Ext}|_{\mathbb{F}}$ is a simple algebra.

Remark Here, we restrict to an arbitrary field $\mathbb{F}$, and so necessarily, we obtain that we are working with a **Fld**-enriched object.

A filter is essentially a *point of connection* which is defined over the transport space of a geometric space. This point of connection gives at least one rule which defines the accessibility of the target of a map to the source. We gave the definition of a 1-filter. For higher orders (i.e., connected *but not* Koszul-connected) of fibrations, we implement instead the concept of an *n-filter*.

Definition 1.0.2 For a covering $\mathbb{Z}/n$ of a topological space, the map into Sets is called an n-filter.

Simply, we say that $n>1$ is an “ultrafilter;” or, any 1-fold covering which admits foliations of $n>1$ is an “ultrafilter.” Whence q is an arbitrary invariant, we write q_{fit} for the filter with respect to q . This is an ultrafilter whence the morphism

$$q \rightarrow]0,1]$$

is split.

Question What would a zero-fold covering look like?

We may extend our construction arbitrarily from discussing *rings/fields* to discussing [Wheels]. We gain an arbitrary and generic object in the category of ∞ -topoi which corresponds to division by zero. Thus, we have an isomorphism between the class of 0-fold coverings and the class of ∞ -topoi. This is substantial, but confusing. In order to differentiate between the two, we need to apply the appropriate *localization*

$$\{\mathbf{Loc}(\hat{q}_{n=0}) \rightarrow \mathbf{Loc}(\hat{q}_{n>0}) \simeq \tau_{>k}(\mu(\hat{q})) \rightarrow \tau_{\neq k}(\mu(\hat{q})) | n>k\}$$

where μ is a *measure* of a neighborhood of $\mathcal{U}(\tilde{\Delta}) \subset \mathbf{S}\mathbf{Sets}$.

1.1.0 Theorem A Zero-fold coverings locally resemble non-zero-valued coverings.

Proof Since we have the inclusion

$$\{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\} \in \mathbf{Cat}_{\infty},$$

and since there is a projective morphism

$$\frac{k}{0} \Vdash \mathbf{Cat}_{\infty},$$

¹ Rank one

we have that the localization of a $\mathbb{Z}/0$ -fold covering is a forcing notion induced by the appropriate choice of k/n as a substitution (projection) of zero.

Axiom 1.1.1a $\text{Spec}(\mathbb{Z}/0)$ is equal to $\aleph_y \in \infty$

Axiom 1.1.1b ∞ is an $\aleph_y$ -cell in the ∞ -category of cardinal invariants

The first of these axioms asserts an equivalence between the spectrum of a zero-fold covering and the appropriate localization to an accessible cardinal. The second guarantees access to localization to any uncountable invariant so long as the parent category is an ∞ -category. Finally,

Axiom 1.1.2 $\text{Hom}(\infty, \infty) \equiv \mathbf{Pow}(\infty)$

states an equivalence “of the strongest kind” between two sets of hom-fibrations of ∞ -categories, and the power set operation on an infinite series of invariants.

Proposition 1.2.0 $\mathcal{Cov}(X, Y)$ is smoothly contained within $\mathbf{Pow}(\infty)$.

Proof The containment is evident from the relationship

$$\mathcal{Cov}(X, Y) \mathbf{R} \mathbf{Pow}(\infty) = \{X_\alpha, Y_\beta\} \subset \infty;$$

that this containment is smooth follows from the fact that for every $\{\alpha, \beta\}$, there is a diagonal

$$\alpha \times \beta: \begin{matrix} L \\ \varepsilon \\ R \end{matrix}$$

which contains every bounded δ_0 -small section in ∞^2 . So,

$$\int_{\varepsilon}^{\infty} \mathcal{Cov}(X, Y) = \langle \varepsilon \rangle^{\heartsuit}$$

and the immersion

$$\mathcal{Cov}(X, Y) \xrightarrow{\varepsilon} \mathbf{Pow}(\infty)$$

is smooth.

This means that all of the Koszul connections of $\mathcal{Cov}(X, Y)$ are *locally of finite type*, and thus are open in any ∞ -category which is isomorphic to *Sets*. This is particularly nice when one wants to work in $\text{Top}_{\Sigma}^{\{*\}, \infty}$ which *strongly models* all locally ringed spaces, including $\mathbb{E}_{\infty}$ -spaces.

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} * & \hookrightarrow & \text{Top}_{\Sigma}^{*, \infty} & \longleftarrow & \infty \\ \updownarrow & & \updownarrow \text{Mod} & & \updownarrow \\ * & \hookrightarrow & \text{Loc}(\Omega_{\Lambda}) & \longleftarrow & \infty \end{array}$$

Figure 1.3.0

² See [Path], Lemma 2

The above commutative diagram relates the appropriate *localization* of a (supposedly symplectic) object with the space of productive topological spaces, or “functored spaces.”³ This is actually an equivalence of extended Kan complexes which states that

$$\text{Hom}(Top_{\Sigma}^{\{*\}, \infty}, Loc(\Omega_{\Lambda})) = \mathcal{K}_{EXT}$$

Here, we take the extension pointwise, and obtain:

$$\lim_{\{*\} \rightarrow \infty} [n] = \infty,$$

the case in which the Kan complex is extended to preserve all the colimits of an ∞ -category.

§1.3.0 Filters on $\mathbf{Or}$

Let $\mathbf{Or}$ be the category of orientation-preserving fibers. Let

$$q_{filt} \mathbf{Or}$$

be a filter on the category of orientation-preserving fibers.

Proposition 1.3.1. If $\mathbf{Or}$ is a monoid, then $q_{filt} \mathbf{Or}$ is monoidal.

Proof A monad satisfies three properties: 1.) closure, 2.) associativity, and 3.) identity.

We see that if $\mathbf{Or}$ satisfies these properties, then a subset $x \subset \mathbf{Or}$ must also be closed; there is an arbitrary extension x^+ of x which allows one to continuously include the members necessary for associativity, which follows from the rule

$$F \star G = G \star F;$$

lastly, if we have an action L corresponding to the q -filter, then we have

$$zero: {}^L \mathbf{Or}_{\{\emptyset\}} \rightarrow 0$$

the zero map as well.

³ See [Inf]

§2 Orientation preserving compass homomorphisms

Recall from §0 that a map of fibers is said to be “orientation preserving” if it is C_p^∞ -linear.

Equivalently, a map $F: X \rightarrow Y$ of fibers said to be an object of **Or** if, and only if there are the chains

$$\mu(X_\alpha, X_\beta, \dots, X_\omega) \infty \mu(Y_\alpha, Y_\beta, \dots, Y_\omega),$$

and if the map $\mu(\mathfrak{X}) \rightarrow \mu(\mathfrak{Y})$ preserves pullbacks of p . In other words, an orientation preserving map is a map of compasses:

$$\Omega_{\mu(\mathfrak{X}) \rightarrow \mu(\mathfrak{Y})}^\infty \rightarrow \Omega_{\mu(\mathfrak{Y}) \rightarrow \mu(\mathfrak{Z})}^\infty$$

where there is an evident natural transformation

$$(-, \mathfrak{Y}) \rightrightarrows (\mathfrak{Y}, \mathfrak{Y}) \cong \mathfrak{X} \Rightarrow \mathfrak{Y}$$